

The Impact of Growth Mindset Intervention on Students at CSUF

by

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Introduction:

Under the national lens, the academic state of the undergraduate experience in the United States does not bode well for the future of the nation. During a time when the national college dropout rate nears 40% and nearly one-third of all first-time college freshman are not returning for their sophomore year (Leary et al., 2020, p. 334), the quest to elucidate a future in which students can stick with and succeed through the academic rigor of advanced college classes remains vital for the country. Even more so, the problem is exacerbated when looking at the demanding course loads of STEM (science, technology, engineering, mathematics) majors and degrees within undergraduate education. For STEM higher education, the gap between students enrolling into STEM programs and those graduating with a STEM degree remains ever so large; in fact, only a stunning 40% of current enrolled undergraduates pursuing STEM majors ever complete their education and receive their degree (President's Council of Advisors on Science and Technology, 2012). Simply put, the state of STEM higher education is in a bad state, and STEM majors themselves are abandoning ship at a rate much faster than we can afford. Even more alarmingly, not all groups of students within STEM disciplines are affected in the same way. First-generation college students and under-represented minority (URM) students often bear the brunt of the high rigor and difficulty of the first two years of STEM education in college. As of 2017, URM students comprised only 21% of STEM bachelor's degrees despite URM groups comprising 30% of the nation (National Science Foundation, 2017, p. 190). Solutions to increase "retention", that is the continued enrollment of students, within the undergraduate higher education system (especially within STEM majors) is of great need for the United States, so much so to the point where the President's Council of Advisors on Science and Technology detailed the crisis of STEM higher education, stating that "transforming STEM education in U.S.

colleges and universities is a daunting challenge” (President’s Council of Advisors on Science and Technology, 2012, p. ii). As the necessity for certifications and degrees in higher education continues to increase, and as the expectation of a diploma in higher education becomes more and more an expected necessity, one thing is clear: STEM degrees are not getting any easier to obtain, but are increasingly needed more than ever.

Given all of these alarming indicators of the state of our undergraduate system, especially in relation to STEM majors, solutions to combat decreasing retention for undergraduates in STEM seem multi-faceted, complex, and hard to implement. But what if there was a solution that started with the students themselves? What if there was a way to naturally tap into a student’s internal capabilities to help them overcome the academic hurdles they face, even in the midst of rigorous challenges, say, the difficulty of grueling STEM courses like organic chemistry or physics? Would a change in students’ internal motivations, their self-perceptions on their capabilities as a “STEM student”, their approach to learning and dealing with complexity, and their interior qualities of perseverance, grit, and persistence be of any real solution towards the retention crisis? This is one of the main national interests in the investigation of STEM education, a field of research which looks at optimal techniques to learn and teach STEM subjects with the goal of increased student retention and improvement of academic success. Oftentimes, as teachers, instructors, students, peers, and fellow classmates, we tend to believe that intelligence is more akin to a talent rather than an improvable skill. The phrase “I’m just not a science person” or “yeah, I just don’t have the brain for math” runs rampant throughout colleges and universities nationwide, but these seemingly benign mentalities are indicative of a deeper problem within the college system, and within the public education system as a whole. Students who display strong academic mastery are not initially viewed as those who have

dedicated the time and effort in practicing and mastering concepts from scratch, but rather “geniuses” and “smart apples” that seem to have this natural ability to excel. This mentality lies not just in the minds of our college students, but also in nature of STEM instruction itself; many STEM courses in the first two years of undergraduate courses are considered “weeder” classes, such as organic chemistry, physics, or genetics, which are perceived to be designed as pathways that filter out those “who don’t have a knack” for STEM subjects. Upon first mention, the immediate impact of changing a student’s mindset is seemingly abstract, and this is precisely why it is most often dismissed as a viable solution to combat undergraduate dropout. However, the work of researcher and child psychologist Carol Dweck in the concepts of growth and fixed mindsets, changed this perception.

A curious scientist drawn to the science of developing psychologies and motivations of young children, Dweck, in her early experiments, investigated how ten-year old children reacted to being presented with complex problems and tasks, ones that would definitely make them struggle and bear with the inherent difficulty of the present problems; in another early experiment, Dweck asked young children the question “When do you feel smart?”, with the purpose of understanding under which context to learning do children find their self-esteem and motivation increased (Dweck and Legget, 1988, p. 226). Dweck saw two groups of students emerge, both with a substantially different outlook to failure, struggle, effort, and perceived ability. The first emergent group displayed a strong negative response in reaction to the complexity and difficulty they encountered; a lot of these students were averse to the risk of failing or struggling, and did not enjoy the need to put in effort to solve a task or problem, but viewed this as a sign of their inability (Dweck and Legget, 1988, p. 226). These students “felt smart” and indicated the highest levels of self-esteem when they breezed through their

homework, got the highest grade, finished problems easily, and beat their peers to assignments. The second emergent group displayed the opposite reaction; they seemed to enjoy the complexity and difficulty they faced, responding with statements like “I love a good challenge!” (Dweck and Legget, 1988, p. 226). These students were much more likely to engage with failure and invest a large amount of effort into tackling difficulty, even if it meant struggling; they “felt smart” when they conquered a hard problem or task and personally mastered it. Dweck noticed that it wasn’t any sort of difference in intellect or ability that separated these two groups, but rather in mindset – she coined two theories to label these mindsets, labeling the first group of students as indicative of the *entity theory* and the second group of students as indicative of the *incremental theory* (Dweck and Legget, 1988, p. 226). Simply put, the entity theory, also known as the fixed mindset, is the belief that when it comes to learning, one’s traits and qualities are inherent and fixed, and that these qualities/traits cannot really change; those who exhibit an entity response of a fixed mindset valued performance as their most important goal, such as making the highest score on a test, setting the curve for the class, or getting the “A” (Dweck and Legget, 1988, p. 226). When it comes to the idea of putting in effort, individuals of the entity response view this as a sign of lack of ability. The incremental theory, also known as the growth mindset, is the belief that when it comes to learning, one’s traits and qualities are not fixed, but are malleable, and can indeed grow and change over time, given effort and practice; those who exhibit an incremental response of a growth mindset are not as much concerned with performing excellently in the classroom as they are actually mastering the given concept or goal in learning (Dweck and Legget, 1988, p. 226). For them, learning/mastery is the most important goal, not performance. For these individuals, struggling and putting in the effort is a sign of progress to mastery and learning, and thus is self-perceived positively, as something to be warranted. Dweck

saw how the difference between a growth mindset and a fixed mindset was the difference between students giving up on the first sign of struggle/difficulty and successfully finishing these complex tasks and problems; this was one of the first definitive signs that the mindset of students holds a precious value towards their academic success. This change in fixed and growth mindset is evident by the physical changes in the brain that also take shape. According to several neurological studies, individuals expressing a growth mindset have been shown to exhibit significantly higher rate of error-related potentials, which are certain neurophysiological firing patterns called error-related potentials that are initiated during moments when an individual is perceiving a mistake or wrong action (Frontiers, 2020), this is “correlated with a heightened awareness of and attention to mistakes” (Ng, 2018, p. 4), and individuals who exhibit a growth mindset are shown to essentially be reprogramming their neural circuits to be more dynamically sensitive to moments of error, mistakes, and struggle, and in those moments, react and change their thinking/processing to adapt.

The evident potential of mindset intervention towards the areas of STEM education that suffer from the aforementioned problems of retention and lack of representation cannot be dismissed; achievement and performance gaps between URM groups and the rest of the student population remain a vital concern, especially in the area of STEM. Remarkably, a study by Angela Fink and colleagues involved the use of a social-psychological, course-based intervention taken by first-year, general chemistry college students showed that the application of “mindset intervention eliminated the racial achievement gap in General Chemistry 1” (Fink et al., 2018, p. 795); mindset intervention may indeed be one of the most practical ways to combat the subtle “sociocultural and academic factors can interact to undermine the performance and long-term persistence of underrepresented groups in STEM” (Fink et al., 2018, p. 785).

For the purposes of this study, we seek to analyze the impact of a mindset intervention implemented in first-year (freshman) students pursuing STEM majors at California State University Fullerton, a public state university that is composed of a large body of minority students, with almost 46.7% of students being Hispanic or Latino. This study asks the following research questions: 1) how do students' mindset change after participating in virtual growth mindset workshops, and 2) after participating in virtual growth mindset workshops, is there a difference in mindset scores between male and female students?

Methods and Design:

The participants of this study were students enrolled in CNSM-101 (Think Like Einstein), a class taken by first-year STEM major students, during the fall semester of 2021. During this semester, this class was taught virtually due to ongoing COVID-19 restrictions. Intervention sessions were held during Week 1 and Week 3, in which students were exposed to a variety of resources on growth mindset, neuroplasticity, the brain's ability to grow or adapt, and more materials pertaining to mindset and its impacts.

Figure 1. The timeline of interventions is shown above for Week 1, Week 3, and Week 13.

Throughout the semester, a mixed-methods approach using pre and post surveys (from the Qualtrics software platform) were sent out to gather both qualitative and quantitative data to

track students' mindsets changes (Figure 1). Students' mindset scores were measured using the "Dweck Mindset Instrument" (DMI), where students rate themselves on a six-point Likert scale indicating their level of agreement or disagreement by assigning each statement a number: 1 (strongly agree) to 6 (strongly disagree). Based on a confirmatory factor analysis on a previous semester's data that Dr. Chan conducted, two constructs (growth and fixed mindset) were identified. Therefore, a student's average "growth score" and average "fixed score" can be calculated by taking the average of specific statements from the DMI. Averaging Q1, 2, 4, and 6 will give a fixed score and averaging Q3, 5, 7, and 8 will give a growth score.

Additionally, qualitative data was collected by asking students to openly respond to reflection questions in the survey, which probed for changes in mindset, student responses to failure, student understanding of concepts of neuroplasticity and changes in the brain, and more.

A)

1. You have a certain amount of intelligence, and you really can't do much to change it.
2. Your intelligence is something about you that you can't change very much.
3. No matter who you are, you can significantly change your intelligence level.
4. To be honest, you can't really change how intelligent you are.
5. You can always substantially change how intelligent you are.
6. You can learn new things, but you can't really change your basic intelligence.
7. No matter how much intelligence you have, you can always change it quite a bit.
8. You can change even your basic intelligence level considerably.

B)

Average Growth Mindset Scores	Average Fixed Mindset Scores
1 (Most Growth) - 6 (Least Growth)	1 (Most Fixed) - 6 (Least Growth)

C)

1. After participating in Growth Mindset workshops (Weeks 1 and 3), how has your attitude and perception towards failure and challenges changed?
2. After participating in Growth Mindset workshops (Weeks 1 and 3), what would you identify as some of the strengths in these two workshops? What improvements would you suggest for future workshops?

Figure 2. A) The statements/phrases of the Dweck Mindset Instrument, applied to students in surveys, are shown. Highlighted statements refer to statements indicative of fixed mindsets, while non-highlighted statements are indicative of growth mindsets. B) The range of measured average growth/fixed scores is shown. *A lower average mindset score indicates a stronger affinity for that particular mindset displayed in the student.* C) Reflection and open-ended response questions that were used to obtain qualitative data on student changes in mindset, attitude, perception to failure, neuroplasticity, and more is shown.

Once the “average growth” and “average fixed” scores were calculated for each student (referred to growth scores and fixed scores from this point on), the degree of kurtosis and skewness of the data set was analyzed. If the degree of kurtosis and skewness within the data set was larger than the statistical standard ($z < 1.96$ or $z > 1.96$), the data statistically contains excess skewness and kurtosis (Appendix I). Since our data contains excess skewness and kurtosis, a series of non-parametric statistical tests were conducted: the Friedman test, the Wilcoxon signed-rank test, and the Mann Whitney U test.

The Friedman test was used to analyze any statistically significant changes in median mindset scores (growth, fixed) across the semester (Weeks 1, 3, and 13). The Wilcoxon signed-rank test was used to analyze any statistically significant changes in students’ mindsets between each two time points (Week 1 to Week 3, Week 1 to Week 13, and Week 3 to 13). The Mann Whitney U test was used to analyze any statistically significant differences between male and female students’ mindset scores (fixed, growth).

Results

For the quantitative data, the collective data sets showed excess levels of both kurtosis and skewness (Appendix I), and thus nonparametric tests were conducted for this study. It should be noted that the equivalent parametric tests were also conducted (i.e., one-way repeated measures analysis of variance (ANOVA), post-hoc comparison test, and independent samples t-test) to determine if the results of the parametric tests corroborate with the non-parametric tests. The same trends were observed using both parametric and non-parametric tests. In this study, we choose to report non-parametric tests based on our skewness and kurtosis tests. To reduce Type I error, we applied a Bonferroni correction to define a standard of significance at $p < 0.008$.

To answer our first research question, a Friedman test was conducted to compare the median growth and fixed scores of all three time points of Week 1, 3, and 13 (Appendix II). Two significant trends were seen: a general decrease in growth scores and a general increase in fixed scores going from Week 1 to Week 13 ($X^2 = 261.1$, $N = 65$, $df = 5$, $p < 0.001$), which translates to a general increase in students' growth mindset and general decrease in students' fixed mindset as the semester had progressed from Week 1 to Week 13, respectively (Figures 3 and 4).

Figure 3. The median growth scores of students of the study are shown above, with a general trend of decreasing growth scores, indicating an increasing extent of growth mindset displayed ($X^2 = 261.1$, $N = 65$, $df = 5$, $p < 0.001$).

Figure 4. The median fixed scores of students are shown above, with a general trend of increasing fixed scores, indicating a decreasing extent of fixed mindset displayed ($X^2 = 261.1$, $N = 65$, $df = 5$, $p < 0.001$).

To further analyze when the changes in mindsets (growth, fixed) took place, a post hoc analysis with the Wilcoxon signed rank test was conducted. The results of the Wilcoxon signed-rank test showed statistically significant changes between Week 1 and Week 3 in both fixed scores and growth scores, and also between Week 1 and Week 13 in only fixed scores (Figures 5 and 6, Appendix III).

Between Week 1 and Week 3, quantitatively shown through mindset scores, 59% of students were increasing in their growth mindset, about 24% were decreasing in their growth mindset, and 17% did not display a change in growth mindset (Figure 5, $N = 84$, $Z = -3.001$, $p < 0.008$). Analogous to the data presented for the growth mindset scores were the similar trends found in students' fixed mindsets over the same period: 62% of students decreased in the fixed

mindset, 20% of students increased in their fixed mindset, and 18% did not display a change in fixed mindset (Figure 6, $N = 84$, $Z = -4.54$, $p < 0.001$).

Figure 5. Changes of students in their growth mindsets are shown above between the timepoints of Week 1 and Week 3 during the semester using the Wilcoxon signed-rank test. A majority of the students exhibit an increasing growth mindset across this time period ($N = 84$, $Z = -3.001$, $p < 0.008$).

Figure 6. Changes of students in their fixed mindsets are shown above between the timepoints of Week 1 and Week 3 during the semester using the Wilcoxon signed-rank test. A majority of the students exhibit a decreasing fixed mindset across this time period ($N = 84$, $Z = -4.54$, $p < 0.001$).

Figure 7. Changes of students in their fixed mindsets are shown above between the timepoints of Week 1 and Week 13 during the semester using the Wilcoxon signed-rank test. A majority of the students exhibit a decreasing fixed mindset across this time period encompassing the whole semester.

From Week 1 to Week 13, 51% of students were decreasing in their fixed mindset, about 27% were increasing in their fixed mindset, and 17% did not display a change in fixed mindset (Figure 7, $N = 166$, $Z = -4.67$, $p < 0.001$). The same trend was seen in growth scores between Week 1 and Week 13, with about 47% of students increasing in their growth mindset, 30% of students decreasing in their growth mindset, and 23% did not display a change in their growth mindset, albeit non statistically significant (Appendix III, $N = 166$, $Z = -1.82$, $p = 0.0609$).

To answer our second research question, the Mann Whitney U test was conducted. Results show that by Week 13, there was indeed a statistically significant difference in students' growth scores, with females ending up with a significantly higher growth score than males

(Appendix IV, $N = 274$, $U = 5942$, $p < 0.001$). In other words, this indicates that by Week 13, females are exhibiting less of a growth mindset than males. This was the only statistically significant finding of the Mann Whitney U test.

Analysis of the qualitative data collected showed changes in students' perceptions and attitude towards failure and challenges, improved responses to encounters with failure, and improved responses to encountering difficulty and addressing challenges in learning, several of the hallmarks of growth mindset, in multiple students in the data set (Table 1). After intervention, an overwhelming majority of students indicated, from partial agreement to strong agreement, that interventions were indeed valuable and that their approach towards challenging topics and situations has changed (Figure 8).

Table 1. Reflection question asked during Week 3 (after completion of two intervention workshops) on Qualtrics survey, as well as student responses to the question. Statements and phrases indicative of positive mindset changes are underlined in red.

Q16: After participating in Growth Mindset workshops (Weeks 1 and 3), how has your attitude and perception towards failure and challenges changed?

"After the Growth Mindset workshops, I now view failure and challenges as an opportunity. Life is full of unexpected situations, and no matter how much I try to avoid failures, there will always be a time where I will face setbacks. So, why not face it head on and learn something new?"

"I have always seen failure as a learning experience, but these workshops have given me the confirmation that to embrace failure is to make yourself more prepared in the future. I face challenges with a positive attitude and use my growth mindset to get better and be better."

"Now I realize the importance of having an open mind and allowing myself to think about how it is okay to fail. I can already see the benefits in this way of thinking. When I experience a setback or challenge, instead of letting it put me down like I used to let it do, I look at it from different sides and overcome come it in a more positive attitude."

Figure 8. Three statements assessing the traits of growth mindset and affirming its benefits/impacts were given to students in the Week 13 survey, and for each statement, almost all students agreed (including strong to somewhat strong levels of agreement).

Discussion and Conclusion:

The results of this study demonstrated the benefits of hosting growth mindset intervention workshops for STEM college students. The intervention's impact in increasing students' growth mindsets and decreasing their fixed mindsets was indeed significant. Not only was there an overall trend of increasing growth mindset and decreasing fixed mindset in the data set collectively as indicated by the Friedman test results, but also between weeks of the intervention as indicated by the Wilcoxon test result. There were statistically significant increases in growth mindset and decreases in fixed mindset between Weeks 1 and 3, as well as an overall significant decrease in fixed mindset and increase in growth mindset from Week 1 to Week 13, collectively. Our results provide support for our first research question, as we have demonstrated a difference and change in student mindsets as a result of intervention. To further determine the magnitude of

change in students' mindsets, future work will include calculating effect sizes for each of the non-parametric tests conducted.

With regards to our second research question that looks into the differential impact of intervention between males and females, less support was seen; the only statistically significant finding was that of the time point, Week 13, in growth scores, with males exhibiting a significantly higher extent of growth mindset (as indicated by their lower growth scores) than females by the end of Week 13 (Appendix IV). This does not mean that female students are displaying more fixed mindsets than male students; from the Mann Whitney U test results alone, the data only showed support for the fact that female students do not obtain as much of the increase in growth mindset as a result of intervention than do male students, and this does not necessarily mean that female students exhibit more of a fixed mindset than male students. However, it is important to note the differences in population sizes of male and female students within the study. For the statistically significant difference in growth scores of Week 13 between males and females, the female population was almost twice as large as the male population, with 190 female students to 84 male students who had completed the Week 13's DMI survey. This was one limitation of the study that does not allow us to conclude any substantial findings for our second research question; a solution to this would be to implement interventions on multiple classes (to increase sample sizes) and aim for representative sizes of populations for both female and male students.

Another aspect of intervention that was observed was the longitudinal impact of intervention, specifically regarding the effect of the gaps of time between the time points of our intervention. The first two time points (Week 1 to 3), allow for a concentrated dose of mindset information and intervention concepts to our students, but the next time point (Week 3 to 13)

presents a sizable gap in time of about ten weeks before reintroducing students to intervention materials and collecting mindset scores once again. The results of the Wilcoxon test, especially for fixed scores, show that from Week 1 to Week 3, about 62% of students were decreasing in fixed mindset (Figure 6), but by Week 13, only about half (51%) of students were decreasing in fixed mindset, showing the gradual attenuation of the mindset intervention's impact due to time; this long ten week gap of time between the two last time points in our intervention (Weeks 3 to 13), a gap that includes the bulk of midterms, exams, and other stressful events in both academic and personal life for all college students, may explain the non-statistically significance in mindset scores from Week 3 to 13. This shows the relative retention of mindset intervention within our study throughout the span of time and points to the potential benefits of the use of a more frequent exposure to intervention that engages students more frequently throughout the semester to promote increased retention and consolidation of mindset information.

Potential future work based on the results of this study include investigating the differential impact of intervention on under-represented minority (URM) groups, and also in investigating different areas of STEM (chemistry, physics, biology) to understand how to tailor and refine intervention towards specific niches within STEM education.

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Appendices:**I. Skewness and Kurtosis Measurements**

	Skewness Statistic	Std. Error	Z	Absolute Value (Z)
Fixed Score (Week 1)	-0.62	0.16	-3.875	3.875
Growth Score (Week 1)	0.862	0.16	5.388	5.388
Fixed Score (Week 3)	-1.017	0.231	-4.403	4.403
Growth Score (Week 3)	1.09	0.231	4.719	4.719
Fixed Score (Week 13)	-0.663	0.147	-4.510	4.510
Growth Score (Week 13)	0.624	0.147	4.245	4.245

*If data sets exhibit (kurtosis) Z scores of more than 1.96 in magnitude, they are considered statistically skewed.

	Kurtosis Statistic	Std. Error	Z	Absolute Value (Z)
Fixed Score (Week 1)	0.474	0.319	-7.918	7.918
Growth Score (Week 1)	1.25	0.319	-5.486	5.486
Fixed Score (Week 3)	1.336	0.459	-3.625	3.625
Growth Score (Week 3)	0.916	0.459	-4.540	4.540
Fixed Score (Week 13)	-0.073	0.293	-10.488	10.488
Growth Score (Week 13)	0.053	0.293	-10.058	10.058

*If data sets exhibit (skewness) Z scores (absolute value) of more than 1.96 in magnitude, they are considered statistically skewed.

II. Friedman Test Measurements

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	25 th Percentile	50 th Percentile (Median)	75 th Percentile
Fixed Score (Week 1)	65	4.6154	0.81139	4.25	4.75	5
Growth Score (Week 1)	65	2.05	0.66761	1.5	2	2.5
Fixed Score (Week 3)	65	5.0808	0.68481	4.75	5	5.625
Growth Score (Week 3)	65	1.7846	0.6986	1.25	1.75	2
Fixed Score (Week 13)	65	4.9192	0.8281	4.625	5	5.5
Growth Score (Week 13)	65	1.8615	0.69742	1.25	1.75	2.5

N	65
Chi-Square	261.147
df	5
Asymp. Sig.	p < .001

III. Wilcoxon Test Measurements

		N	Asymp. Sig. (two-tailed)	Z
Fixed Score (Week 1 to Week 3)	Negative Ranks	17		
	Positive Ranks	52	< 0.001	-4.540
	Ties	15		
	Total	84		

Fixed Score (Week 1 to Week 13)	Negative Ranks	44		
	Positive Ranks	85	< 0.001	-4.671
	Ties	37		
	Total	166		
Fixed Score (Week 3 to Week 13)	Negative Ranks	32	0.143	-1.464
	Positive Ranks	27		
	Ties	28		
	Total	87		
Growth Score (Week 1 to Week 3)	Negative Ranks	50	0.003	-3.001
	Positive Ranks	20		
	Ties	14		
	Total	84		
Growth Score (Week 1 to Week 13)	Negative Ranks	78	0.069	-1.820
	Positive Ranks	49		
	Ties	39		
	Total	166		
Growth Score (Week 3 to Week 13)	Negative Ranks	25	0.096	-1.662
	Positive Ranks	36		
	Ties	26		
	Total	87		

IV. Mann Whitney U Test Measurements

	Sex	N	Mean Rank	Asymp. Sig. (two-tailed)
Fixed Score (Week 1)	Female	163	113.06	0.297
	Male	68	123.06	
	Total	231		
Growth Score (Week 1)	Female	163	119.32	0.238
	Male	68	108.04	
	Total	231		
Fixed Score (Week 3)	Female	77	58.81	0.049
	Male	32	45.83	
	Total	109		
Growth Score (Week 3)	Female	77	51.4	0.062
	Male	32	63.66	
	Total	109		
Fixed Score (Week 13)	Female	190	131.11	0.043
	Male	84	151.96	
	Total	274		
Growth Score (Week 13)	Female	190	148.23	< 0.001
	Male	84	113.24	
	Total	274		